

Information Security Roles and Responsibilities

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Revision History

Version	Date	Created By	Description of Changes
1.0	03/15/2026	Stefan Krauss (ISM)	Initial release of Roles and responsibilities Framework defining ISMS governance structure and role definitions.

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1. Purpose

The purpose of this document is to define the leadership structure, roles, responsibilities, authority, and oversight mechanisms required to establish, implement, maintain, and continually improve the Information Security Management System (ISMS).

2. Scope

This framework applies to all personnel, functions, and organizational units within the scope of the Information Security Management System (ISMS), as defined in the ISMS Scope Statement.

3. Roles and Responsibilities

3.1. Information Security Committee (ISC)

Role

The Information Security Committee (ISC) is the organization's single governing body for the Information Security Management System (ISMS). It provides executive-level oversight of information security risks and ensures that security decisions align with business objectives, risk appetite, and operational priorities.

Members

- Chief Executive Officer (Sponsor)
- Chief Technology Officer
- Chief Financial Officer
- Information Security Manager (Chair)
- Key functional representatives as required

Responsibilities

- Approve the ISMS Scope
- Approve the Information Security Policy
- Define and approve the information security objectives
- Define and approve the organization's risk appetite and risk acceptance criteria
- Approve risk treatment decisions
- Review risk assessment results
- Monitor progress of risk treatment plans
- Review ISMS performance
- Ensure adequate resources are allocated to the ISMS
- Approve risk treatment decisions

- Approve security budgets and investment initiatives
- Resolve cross-departmental security conflicts
- Act as crisis leadership during major security incidents

Meetings

- Quarterly meetings focused on performance metrics and decision-making
- Emergency sessions for major incidents or changes
- Meetings are metric-driven, dashboard-supported, decision-focused and time-bound

3.2. Information Security Manager (ISM)

Role

Operational leadership role responsible for the implementation, coordination, and continuous operation of the Information Security Management System (ISMS), including chairing the Information Security Committee.

Responsibilities

- Maintain and operate the ISMS
- Conduct and coordinate risk assessments
- Maintain and update the risk register
- Monitor control effectiveness and ISMS performance metrics
- Coordinate internal audits and compliance reviews
- Ensure alignment with ISO 27001 requirements
- Lead governance-level incident coordination
- Report ISMS metrics and risk posture to the Information Security Committee

Chair Responsibilities

- Set the Information Security Committee agenda
- Prepare and present risk dashboards and ISMS performance reports
- Facilitate committee meetings
- Ensure tracking and closure of action items
- Coordinate cross-functional follow-up on decisions
- Maintain ISMS documentation and audit evidence
- Trigger emergency committee sessions when required

Authority

- Request information and evidence from any department
- Recommend risk treatment strategies
- Propose updates to policies and controls
- Escalate risks directly to Executive Leadership
- Trigger emergency governance sessions

3.3. Asset Owners

Role

Asset Owners are individuals or designated business functions responsible for the proper management, classification, and protection of information assets throughout their lifecycle.

Ownership in this context does not imply legal ownership, but rather accountability for ensuring that assets are appropriately classified, protected, and used in line with organizational requirements.

Responsibilities

- Ensure the asset register is accurate for their assets
- Define appropriate classification for assigned assets
- Ensure assets are protected according to their classification level
- Define acceptable use and handling requirements for assets
- Approve access requirements in coordination with system administrators or custodians
- Ensure assets remain aligned with business and security requirements throughout their lifecycle
- Participate in risk assessments related to assigned assets
- Ensure compliance with applicable security policies and controls

Authority

- Assign classification levels to owned asset
- Approve or reject access requirements for assigned assets
- Require implementation of security controls related to asset protection
- Request remediation of risks affecting assigned assets

3.4. Risk Owners

Role

Risk Owners are individuals or business functions responsible for the management of specific information security risks, including their assessment, treatment, and ongoing monitoring.

A Risk Owner is typically the person or function most closely associated with the asset, process, or activity that gives rise to the risk.

Responsibilities

- Own assigned risks within the Risk Register

- Participate in risk identification and assessment activities
- Define and implement risk treatment actions in coordination with relevant stakeholders
- Monitor the status and effectiveness of risk treatment plans
- Ensure risks remain within defined risk appetite and acceptance criteria
- Provide updates on risk status to the Information Security Committee
- Escalate risks that exceed defined tolerance levels

Authority

- Propose and implement risk treatment options (mitigation, transfer, avoidance, acceptance)
- Request support from Asset Owners, technical teams, or third parties for risk treatment
- Recommend risk acceptance where appropriate within defined governance thresholds
- Escalate high or critical risks to Executive Leadership or the ISMS Manager

3.5. All Users**Role**

All Users include any individual with access to the organization's information systems, data, or assets. This includes employees, contractors, interns, and any third parties acting on behalf of the organization.

Responsibilities

- Comply with all applicable information security policies and procedures
- Use information systems and assets only for authorized business purposes
- Report suspected or actual security incidents, vulnerabilities, or policy violations
- Complete mandatory security awareness and training activities

Authority

- Access only the information and systems explicitly authorized to them
- Report security concerns without fear of retaliation
- Request clarification on security policies and acceptable use when needed

4. Document Maintenance

This document shall be reviewed at least annually and updated as necessary in response to organizational, regulatory, or structural changes.